

IMPROVING THE TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF ACUTE TONSILLITIS IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *The aim of the study was to develop ways to improve the effectiveness of treatment and secondary prevention of acute tonsillitis in children at the primary healthcare level.*

The study included 212 children with acute tonsillitis being treated at Family Polyclinic No. 25 in Tashkent and at the Central Polyclinic of the Kibray District in Tashkent Region, as well as 110 healthy children.

The research subject included saliva, peripheral blood, and throat swabs.

Keywords: *acute tonsillitis, children's saliva, blood, neutrophils, lymphocytes, throat swab, immunity.*

Relevance. In the last thirty years, there has been an increase in the incidence of upper respiratory tract diseases in children and adolescents with acute inflammation in the world [1]. As noted in the World Health Organization's 2020 report "World failing to provide children with a healthy life and a climate fit for their future: WHO-UNICEF-Lancet", "...Despite the successes achieved in improving the health of children and adolescents over the past 20 years, progress in this area has slowed down, and at some point the reverse process will begin...", which is fraught with impact on children's health (WHO, 2020).

New methods have been developed in the world in the field of treatment and diagnosis of various diseases. Nevertheless, acute tonsillitis is one of the most common diseases in the work of a family doctor [1,2,3,4]. Acute tonsillitis occupies a leading place in terms of demand for treatment and preventive work, and 14.4-38.6% of sick children visiting a clinic are children with acute tonsillitis [2].

In Uzbekistan, respiratory diseases remain one of the highest among all diseases of the child population, and its growth continues [3]. One of such pathological processes is acute tonsillitis. The problem of acute tonsillitis remains unchanged from both a social and medical point of view, being a stable direction of modern pediatrics [5,6,7,8,9,16].

In our country, a lot of work is being done to improve the health care system and social protection of the population, adapt the medical system to the requirements of world standards, early diagnosis, treatment and prevention of diseases. In raising the level of medical care for the population to a new level, the tasks aimed at "... the introduction of modern methods of diagnosis and treatment, the provision of high-quality medical services, including the introduction and development of telemedicine ..." ² were identified. In implementing these tasks, it is desirable to prevent the spread of various skin diseases among the population, raise the level of modern medical care to a new level, use modern technologies, develop effective methods of treatment and prevention [10,11,12].

A study of the scientific literature of recent years shows that in modern pediatrics much attention is paid to the problem of timely initiation of treatment and prevention of acute upper respiratory tract diseases in children, in particular, acute tonsillitis [13,14,15]. This is mainly due

to the fact that acute tonsillitis is one of the common diseases among the child population, with about 600 million cases registered annually worldwide (Dan JM, Havenar-Daughton C et al., 2019; Strzelczyk JK et al., 2022). This problem has been studied by leading foreign scientists and it has been noted that the irrational use of antibiotics leads to a decrease in general immunity and a negative effect on the microflora of the pharynx (Rivera-Hernandez T, 2019; Abdel-Naby Awad OG., 2020; Safak AS et al., 2022). The variability of the tonsil microbiota in acute tonsillitis has been proven, where Streptococcus, Staphylococcus and Prevotella come to the fore, prevailing up to 80-95% in relation to the indicators of practically healthy people (Nilsson AS, 2019; Naegeli A et al., 2019). At the same time, the most common potentially pathogenic microflora are: group A beta-hemolytic streptococcus - Streptococcus pyogenes (31.3%) Staphylococcus aureus (31%), Haemophilus influenzae (11.3%), and Streptococcus Pneumoniae (8.4%), (Chanishvili N. 2018).

At the same time, Russian scientists also note that the treatment of acute tonsillitis should be approached taking into account the immune status of children (Karpishchenko S.A. et al., 2018; Gorbacheva E.V. et al., 2019).

In the clinical practice of a family doctor, there is often a need for rational use of antibacterial drug therapy. The effectiveness of using bacteriophages in pediatrics increases the effectiveness of treatment to 25-48% (Filippova I., 2021; Nikiforova G.N. et al., 2021; Kirichenko I.M., 2018). At the same time, the issue of the use of bacteriophages in the treatment of acute tonsillitis and its effect on the immune status of the oral cavity remains open.

In Uzbekistan, the immune status of the oral cavity was studied in older patients in terms of dental diseases (Rizaev Zh.A., 2019; Nazarova N.Sh., 2020), but the issue of its study in children with acute inflammatory diseases of the upper respiratory tract requires a solution.

It should be noted that, despite the presence of many studies on this pathology, the issue of treating acute tonsillitis remains complex. The most important problem is that the disease mainly occurs in children and effective methods of treatment and prevention have not been fully developed.

The purpose of the study is to develop ways to improve the effectiveness of treatment and secondary prevention of acute tonsillitis in children at the primary health care level.

The object of the study was 212 sick children with acute tonsillitis who were treated in Family Clinic No. 25 in Tashkent and in the Central Clinic of the Kibray district of the Tashkent region and 110 healthy children.

The subject of the study were saliva, peripheral blood, and a pharyngeal swab.

Research methods. General clinical, immunological, microbiological, clinical-instrumental, paraclinical and statistical research methods were used in the work.

Research results.

A total of 322 children and adolescents aged 4 to 15 years (average age 9.5 ± 2.37 years) living in Tashkent and the Tashkent region were examined. Of these, 212 children and adolescents were diagnosed with acute tonsillitis of various clinical forms, as well as 110 children similar in gender and age characteristics, without pronounced somatic and neuropsychological pathology, who were included in the control group. A total of 177 (54.97%) male children and adolescents and 145 (45.03%) female children and adolescents were examined.

Depending on the treatment tactics, all the examined children were divided into study groups (Table 1). The first study group (I-OG) included children and adolescents with acute

tonsillitis during the period of illness, whose treatment was based only on standard therapy (n=107; 50.47% of the total number of sick children - n=212).

Table 1.

Division of children and adolescents into groups

	KG (n=110)		1- surveyed group (n=107)		2- surveyed group (n=105)		Total	
	n	% (Within group)	n	% (Within group)	n	% (Within group)	n	%
Boys	55	50	62	57,94	60	57,14	177	54,97
Girls	55	50	45	42,06	45	42,86	145	45,03
Total	110	32,64	107	31,75	105	32,64	322	100,0

The second examined group (II-OG) included children and adolescents with acute tonsillitis during the period of illness, in the treatment of which bacteriophage therapy was used together with standard treatment (n=105; 49.53% of the total number of sick children – n=212). Depending on the age category, all examined children and adolescents were divided into age groups (Table 2).

Table 2.

Age distribution of the examined children

	Control group (n=110)				I - surveyed group (n=107)				II - surveyed group (n=105)				Total				Total	
	4-8* years		9-15 years		4-8* years		9-15 years		4-8* years		9-15 years		4-8* years		9-15 years			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	N	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
Boys	27	49,10	28	50,90	34	54,84	28	62,22	33	55,93	27	58,70	94	53,41	83	56,85	177	54,97
Girls	28	50,90	27	49,1	28	45,16	17	37,78	26	44,07	19	41,30	82	46,59	63	43,15	145	45,03
Total	55	50,0 of 110	55	50,0 of 110	62	57,94 of 107	45	42,06 of 107	59	56,19 of 105	46	43,81 of 105	176	54,66 of 322	146	45,34 of 322	322	100

Note: * from 4 years to 8 years 11 months 29 days

Such age classification was due to the need to study the clinical and laboratory features of the course of OT in each age group. Treatment of children with acute tonsillitis was based on generally accepted clinical recommendations, and was of a pronounced symptomatic nature with the inclusion of antibacterial therapy based on the results of bacteriological research.

Based on the tasks set before us, clinical and laboratory research methods included: clinical examination of patients, instrumental and clinical and laboratory research. After collecting the anamnestic data of patients, a general clinical examination was carried out, including pharyngoscopy from instrumental studies. Clinical and laboratory research methods included: general clinical studies (complete blood count with a detailed white blood cell count and calculation of the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio - NLR), immunological studies (mucosal immunity study: quantitative determination of secretory immunoglobulin (sIgA, $\mu\text{g/ml}$) and proinflammatory cytokine TNF- α (tumor necrosis factor-alpha pg/ml); bacteriological study of the pharyngeal microbiota.

During the collection of anamnestic data, it was noted that the high seasonality of acute tonsillitis (AT) occurs mainly in the winter-spring period of the year, in particular, in winter, acute tonsillitis was noted in 42% ($n=89$) of patients, in spring - in 34% ($n=72$), in autumn in 20.2% ($n=43$) of patients. Despite the hot climate in the summer of Central Asia, acute tonsillitis was suffered 3.8% ($n=8$) of children. When making a diagnosis, the ICD.10 classification (J03.0-9) was strictly observed.

On the day of seeking outpatient care, the patients noted: asthenovegetative disorders - $n=212$ (100%), in the form of general weakness - $n=209$ (96.8%), decreased appetite - $n=201$ (94.8%), headache - $n=196$ (92.5%). Objectively: lymphadenopathy - $n=208$ (98.6%), hyperemia of the tonsils - $n=212$ (100%), hyperplasia - $n=208$ (98.1%), the occurrence of exudates - $n=102$ (48.1%).

At the same time, all patients complained of periodic hyperthermia - $n=212$ (100%). When considering the clinical course of OT depending on the age category, the same incidence of asthenovegetative symptoms was recorded in all age groups. At the same time, in children from the younger age group, the following prevailed from the asthenovegetative syndrome: headache - 97.5% versus 85.7%, decreased appetite - 97.5% versus 85.7%, ($p \geq 0.05$), which prevails by an average of 11.8%. At the same time, for this group of children, swelling of the tonsils was more typical 94.2% versus 82.4%, the occurrence of exudates - 61.2% versus 30.8%, ($p \leq 0.05$). The obtained data indicate the prevalence of local clinical manifestations in younger children by an average of 21.1%, and a more severe course in children of preschool and primary school age. Based on the objective of our study, patients from the second group ($n=105$; 49.5% of 212) were simultaneously prescribed PCL along with standard treatment.

As the results of clinical observation showed, the following was noted during treatment: decreased swelling in the tonsils already by the 2nd-3rd day of treatment, a decrease in general signs of intoxication was noted.

At the same time, on the 6th day of conservative treatment, in children from group I of the disease, asthenovegetative disorders persisted in 38.3% of cases, while in children from group II this figure was 17.1%, and these were mainly: general weakness (34.6% and 15.2%), decreased appetite (26.2% and 14.3%), persistence of periodic headaches (29% and 11.4%, respectively), ($p \leq 0.05$).

The obtained data showed that despite complex conservative treatment in outpatient settings, general signs of intoxication persist on the 6th day of therapy. At the same time, given the definition in the analysis of peripheral blood of the picture of anemia, as a consequence of intoxication and malnutrition in OT, the anemia itself aggravates the course of asthenovegetative disorders in patients.

At the same time, in patients who received inhalation bacteriophage therapy, asthenovegetative disorders were manifested 2.2 times less in relation to patients from group I. This condition can be characterized by the fastest removal of intoxication of the body, due to the immunostimulating and local antibacterial effect of bacteriophages.

When analyzing local changes, we noted the persistence of cervical lymphadenopathy in 41.1% and 36.2% of patients, respectively, on the 6th day, indicating an extended recovery period in the lymphoid tissue, but at the same time, local pathological changes in patients from group II are restored on average 1.4 times faster compared to patients from group I.

As our studies have shown, after a course of antibacterial therapy, on the 6th day of conservative treatment, the incidence of *Streptococcus pyogenes* decreases from 53.3% to 4.7%, *Staphylococcus aureus* - from 35.5% to 4.7%, and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* - from 26.2% to 3.7%, which is an average 8.7-fold decrease in the frequency of detection of these bacteria. At the same time, the use of a combination of antibiotic therapy with bacteriophage therapy on the 6th day of treatment leads to an average of more than 30-fold decrease in the detection of these bacteria. Therefore, starting from the first days of combined use of antibiotics with bacteriophage therapy, it is possible to increase the effectiveness of drug therapy for patients with acute tonsillitis by 4 times.

Based on the task of the scientific work set before us, immunological studies of children and adolescents with OT were conducted before and after combined treatment.

As our studies have shown, the level of sIgA changes depending on the treatment tactics, age category and gender of patients.

In particular, in the control group, in children of the older age group, in relation to the younger age group, the sIgA level was 128.08 ± 10.074 versus 99.49 ± 4.447 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (1.3 times higher, $p \leq 0.05$), also in girls, on average, up to 2% sIgA content prevailed ($p \geq 0.05$), a decrease in sIgA was observed in the acute period of the disease on average in younger children - up to 40.9%, in older children up to 41.9%, ($p \leq 0.05$).

Against the background of combined treatment using bacteriophage therapy, an increase in sIgA was noted on the 6th day of treatment in younger patients up to 97.2%, in older patients up to 97.2% ($p \leq 0.05$ compared to the control group), in patients who received only standard treatment, these figures were 75.8% and 81.6%, respectively ($p \leq 0.05$ compared to the control group). The difference between the two study groups was: between patients in the younger age group - 21.4%, in the older age group - 16.1% ($p \leq 0.05$ compared to the control group), which indicates a highly effective effect of the drug in patients from younger age groups. Similar changes were noted when analyzing the results of the study of the proinflammatory cytokine TNF- α (TNF- α), which makes it possible to assess the functioning and response of the immune system in these patients, and at the same time predict the effectiveness of the therapy.

During the treatment, a gradual decrease in the level of TNF- α was noted. In particular, on the 3rd day of treatment, in children from the I-examined group against the background of inhalation bacteriophage therapy, a decrease in TNF- α to 9.48 ± 0.847 pg/ml was noted, which is on average 11.7% lower compared to patients from the II-examined group (10.71 ± 1.041 pg/ml, $p \leq 0.05$).

Conclusion.

1. The clinical manifestation of acute tonsillitis depends on the age category of children, in particular, in children of the younger age group, asthenovegetative symptoms occur on average in 11.8%, local manifestations are 21.1% more common in relation to children from the older age group, ($p \leq 0.05$).

2. The results of microbiological studies showed that the main representatives of the tonsil microbiota in acute tonsillitis before treatment are Streptococcus pyogenes (56.1% of 212 analyzes), Staphylococcus aureus (33.5%), Streptococcus pneumoniae (25.5%). With joint colonization, 81.7% is dominated by streptococcal bacteria.

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